

The Impact of Digital Human Resource Management in Day to Day Practices of HRM

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Introduction

The development of technology has improved individuals, organizations and the society. It continues to bring changes and impact in the society many ways. The recent technological development insists that people and organizations adopt and accept that the digital innovations to get accommodated in this fast-changing world and environment.

In order to create a modern organization, the ability to adopt continuous changes are required at all levels in an organization. However, the impact of digitalization at all levels in the organization is unavoidable in the recent context. The usage of digital equipment in organizations will replace the human works. This digitalization will not only change the communication process between two individuals or groups, but also will bring out new dimension how the organization functions on themselves, which help to bring big changes in any personnel.

In recent years, most of the software companies have decided not to sell their products in physical package to the customers hence introduced new method called online selling or cloud- based selling. Hence this new idea helped their customers to buy their product through online instead of buying a physical package also they can choose the subscription as per their convenience and need not to worry about any physical damages of the product since it is a virtual product. This digital based sales leads to the new way of working style saving time and money; therefore it is a completely new role for Human Resources function.

Need and Importance of Digital Human Resource Management

The evolving role of HRM has shifted its management through automation, engagement, integration to “team centric productivity and work management” - Amit Banerjee, Vice-Chancellor, SOA Deemed University. Human Resources Management professionals must adapt to the new technological advancement to cope with changing times.

Concept of Digitalization

According to the Human Resource Managers, it is an ongoing essential process for organizations that handles digitalization. The concept of digitalization impacts organization at all levels as it is perceived as a necessary change in our day to day life of HRM. The digitalization brings lot of behavioral changes in terms of communication, handling internal and external customers. Digitalization is not only a technology, but it also changes the behavior of an individual. Hence the Human Resources Manager must understand the need and importance of digitalization and its impact across the globe.

Digitalization of HRM is to improve the day to day activities of organizations and employees behavior. It helps to fulfill their mission and support the employees to understand how digitalization helps to reach the goals of an organization. The digitalization process's main aim is to integrate people and process with equal importance. Hence, the digital tools usage must be used in HRM day-to-day practices to bring out the expected outcomes.

The Knowledge of Digitalization

The concept of "Digitalization" is a new learning for the HR managers to value experience when talent hunt takes place and brings out transformation and creates impact on HRM. Hence the HR manager must undergo training to improve their competencies and create a "digital awareness". The values of digital skills are evident in order to be more competitive and to have a potential that offers to meet the need and goals of the Human Resource Managements' through digital solution. Through digitalization we can manage with unknown people in remote locations.

Essential of DHRM in Day Today Life

The young generation are more "tech-savvy" and spend most of their time with internet and social media, thus there is change in their behavior, skill and personality when compare to the past generations. This technical knowledge helps the younger generations to complete their task in a fast way- saving time and energy. Having these technically sound young generations, the office must be equipped with digital devices in order to engage them in their job. These digital employees are multi-task oriented, technically qualified and like networking. The core function of Human Resource Management is planning a strategy to integrate all departments to create a digital workforce.

Approach of Digital HRM for Execution

The digitalization process is aligned with all the departmental activities to bring out the desired results in an organization. The role of Human Resource Manager is to align all their employees to accomplish organization's goals to make organization more excellence. Though the policies are framed by administrators of the organization but the implementation can be done only by Human Resource Managers hence they must implement effectively. For effective implementation, the HRM uses the digital way of implementation and reduces errors and increases the effectiveness.

Digital HRM Reforms in Organization

The recent technological development helps the organizations to do things easier by following the technical procedures and getting things done faster and under the budget. The major reforms are brought out in fields of recruitment, data storage, communication; financial services etc., Digitalization helps to prepare error free reports and budget in given time frame. When it comes to communication the cost and time are saved. The recruitment strategies and style have changed after the implementation of digitalization, online forms and, video conferencing methods, using

third party app for video calling etc are new addition in recruitment. The government offices have improved a lot when digitalization has taken place in their day today HR practices eg: online attendance, payroll system, e-governance etc. It replaces all traditional methods of practices and made them technologically advanced offices and helps for the improvement of effective organization.

Digitalization of HRM and Employer and Employees Relationship

It creates an environment for the benefit of both employer and employee. The digitalization of HRM is the bridge between management and workers. The grievances of the employees will be addressed with immediate effect and make the employees happy in their job. The digitalization process helps management to do their job with less error. The employer and employee relationship is effective with digitalization in regulatory compliance, settlement of wages and negotiation of wages and other disciplinary functions. Thus, the relationship between employer and employee is cordial with the support of Digitalization of HRM.

Digitalization as a Transforming Instrument in Organization

The transformation happens because of adopting and accepting the changes and willingness to implement and accepting things. In our day to day life there will be lot of changing and rescheduling in our plans, actions, rules and approaches when focusing on desired results by following the certain strategies. The role of Human Resource Manager is to make all the employees undergo a learning session to have knowledge of new arrivals in organization. This will help them to cope and compete with other employees to increase their performance, come up with new ideas and views and make them equipped to accept the changes. The main role of Human Resource Manager is to motivate his employees to accept and adopt the changes, especially digital innovations. Because digitalization helps the organization to bring out the real transformation day to today practices of HRM, it saves time, cost and energy.

The adaptation of digitalization is an important technological advancement in banking sector to provide a quality service to their customers. This provides loyalty to the customers by reducing human errors. Digitalization in the banking sector it's not a choice but it is mandatory. The banks customer's habits are changing every year in order to get better and speedy service. The benefit of digitalization is that it helps to improve the customer service also helps to save time for customers and cost for banking by using cashless transactions and ATMs. Is that helps to improve the customers for banking and revenue. The cashless transaction also helps to secure money whenever dealing with huge amount. The impact of digitalization makes the job easier when opening the bank account, transactions like deposit, money transfer and online buying etc., Also digitalization of banking eliminates gaps between urban and rural. The errors are minimized and hence the productivity is increased.

The digitalization plays a vital role in present passport service all over India. Most of people in India are agreeing that applying for new passport and renewal of passport is easy (collaboration with TCS - Public Private Partnership) when compare to ten years ago. Applying for passport is available online and the system will allot the slots for appointment immediately after submitting the online application and the person can visit the passport office for further process. After the approval the applicant can track the status of application and they send the communication through mail and message. We have more than 100 Passport Seva all over India and dealing more than one lakh applicants every day.

Digitalization has played a significance role in rural development in India and it makes the villages to become economically sound. The evolution of ICT (Information Communication and

Technology) in our country has had a remarkable impact in urban as well as rural areas. According to the market research the usage of DTH is comparatively high in rural areas compared to urban areas. The customers for DTH from rural area are 75%. The Village Information Centre helps in more farmers to take the advice on agriculture and this yields good result in production of food grains. This digitalization helps in creating more employment opportunities in rural areas, improves their life style and living standard, increasing literacy rates etc.

Practical Challenges and Difficulties in Digitalization of Human Resource Management

When creating awareness about digitalization amongst employees to understand the process and importance of digitalization, usage of applications and tools, shifting from traditional to modern digital administration is found difficult. The elderly employees or aged employees are not willing to shift their routine traditional way of doing things to internet or cloud based. The money and time spent for changing the process from paper to digital needs to be considered. Matching the skills between young generation and elderly person is tough when the change takes place.

Conclusion

Change is the only thing which has ever changed. Hence, we must be ready to accept the changes in our day-to-day life. The technical advancement helps to minimize errors and reduce time. Human Resource Management must focus on the challenges to compete with day to day problems in organization. This will help the Human Resource Manager to equip all their employees make them technically sound thus leading to achieve goals in an easier way. The digitalization of Human Resource Management helps to equip the employees of the organization to achieve the organization`s vision and mission in an effective way.

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